

Article Arrival Date**22.11.2024****Article Published Date****20.12.2024****THE EFFECTS OF THE TÜRKİYE CENTURY MAARİF MODEL WORKSHOP-SUPPORTED LANGUAGE EDUCATION ON STUDENTS' LANGUAGE SKILLS AND MOTIVATION****Bilal BUDAK**

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ABSTRACT

Despite the fact that parents and students attach great importance to language education in our country, it is evaluated that the desired success is not at the desired level. Language education should not be limited to schools, but should be spread throughout life. One of the biggest reasons for not learning a language is the lack of exposure. The second important reason can be shown as the level of interest and desire of the students. For these reasons, it was decided to conduct Workshop-Based Language Education. First, a workshop was opened where students can do listening, speaking, reading and writing activities outside of normal class hours. In this workshop, both normal language lessons are taught and learning environments are provided where students can spend time in their other times. An interactive studio workshop was also opened as an integration to our workshop. In the research, a single group pre-test post-test simple experimental model was used from quantitative research methods. The universe of the research is high school students, and the sample is 9th and 10th grade students studying in a secondary school in Kayseri. Within the scope of the study, "English Placement Test (Intermediate)" was created to determine the language skill levels of the students. In addition, a 3-month "Workshop-Based Language Education Program" was prepared. When the results of the pre-test and the post-test repeated after the program were analyzed, it can be said that the foreign language education given in the workshops was beneficial. In addition, monthly English magazines were published under the name of "SEZENGLISH" within the scope of the workshop studies. English-Turkish, Turkish-English book translations were done. Our students' practice exams were held in the interactive studio workshop, which is a language workshop and an integrated workshop. The practice exams were mostly performance-based (Theater, podcast, presentation, etc.). It was determined that these studies caused a significant increase in the students' language level and encouraged them to learn the language in non-school environments. Considering the problems in language education, lack of exposure and students' reluctance, it can be said that workshop-based language education is beneficial in increasing students' motivation and level of English.

Keywords: Workshop, language education, interactive.**1. INTRODUCTION**

Education is a whole with many components. One leg of education stands in the past and the other leg is a door that opens horizons to the future of humanity. The Türkiye Century Education Model, which aims at the peak of material development with a set of national and spiritual values, is a holistic model consisting of the basic approach of the curriculum, student profile, Virtue Value-Action Framework, and skills framework components (MEB, 2024). The physical environments in this holistic model have an important place in both academic development and the production of moral values. Within the physical environments, workshops are shown as areas where practical skills are learned within the scope of the new curriculum. For a

contemporary workshop system, a system based on project work addressed within the context of the course period and the course should be developed; creativity, the development of the art it addresses, the current situation should be addressed, and a system based on a holistic project should be created (Öztütüncü, 2016).

Foreign languages are a fact that everyone has accepted and wanted to learn in the past and today. Changes in foreign language teaching in our country date back to the Tanzimat period. After this period, it was seen that the influence of eastern languages in foreign language education decreased significantly and on the contrary, there was an interest in western languages (Demirel, 2003). The fact that foreign languages were seen as a necessity started in the Republican period. The reason for this is that the education of western languages was seen as very important. It is seen that the desired level was not reached in the process of learning and teaching foreign languages despite the fact that different methods have been tried since the Tanzimat period. Of course, there are many different reasons for this situation. According to Acat and Demiral (2002), although learning a foreign language has become a necessity today, many problems are encountered in coping with this necessity. The most important of these problems is the lack of motivation levels of foreign language learners. Another problem encountered during the language learning period is the pressure placed on learners. These pressures cause language learners to lose their desire, see the language as a necessity and face the fear of making mistakes while learning (Kahraman, 2019). Altan (2017) states that the human brain is designed to learn rather than to be taught, and because this is not known, our classrooms are not learning-centered. He says that the design of the classrooms, the materials in them, and the number of students in the classroom also hinder physical mobility. Another problem in language education is exposure. Since learners are not exposed to the language enough, the desired level of success cannot be achieved. Exposure to the language is seen as one of the most important factors for learning the 4 basic skills both in the school environment and outside of school (Küçükler & Sulac, 2021). One of the indispensable elements in language education is the desire and interest of the learners, that is, the students. Students who do not have enough desire to learn the language prevent the learning environment in the classroom and are not interested in the language at all outside the classroom. On the other hand, students who are interested in the language and want to learn it can develop and learn language skills even in environments outside of school. One of the most common problems in the education and training system is that language learning is seen as a course and compared with the grades received in exams. Based on these and similar problems in language learning, we started our research with the aim of how we can teach a foreign language better. For this reason, we have initiated a study in which our students will be exposed to the language more, will be able to motivate themselves with the studies and will think of this as an internal motivation rather than an obligation. The questions of this research are: Is workshop-based language education beneficial? and does group work in the workshop increase students' awareness of the language? Our purpose is to make language education and learning more active and effective. In addition, we aimed to increase our students' awareness, create special study areas for them, use the 4 basic skills effectively and obtain a product at the end of this research. The difference of our study from other studies is that it includes workshop-based education, provides environments suitable for language learning, directs students to group work and produces products such as magazines, books, brochures and podcasts at the end of the process. Our hypothesis when we started our research was "students can learn the language more effectively and efficiently by providing workshop-based education in foreign language education".

2. METHOD

In the study, a single group pre-test post-test experimental model was used, which is one of the quantitative research methods. In this research method, the independent variable is applied to a

single group. The independent variable in our study is the workshop-based education given to the students for 3 months. The dependent variable is the foreign language levels and awareness of the students. Before such studies are conducted, a pre-test is applied to the research group, and then a post-test is performed to calculate the difference between the means. This difference reveals the degree of effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable (Büyüköztürk, 2007). The universe of the study is students learning a foreign language at the secondary school level, and the sample is 9th and 10th grade students, consisting of 30 people, studying at a high school in Kayseri. The stratified sampling method was used in sample selection. The total of the elements selected from the universe and representing the whole is called the sample (Ural, 2011). The “English Placement Test (Intermediate)”, which includes 4 basic skills, was used as the data collection tool in the study. These 4 basic skills include speaking, reading, listening and writing activities. In addition, a 3-month workshop-based education program was prepared and this program was implemented in the foreign language workshop outside of class hours and in the interactive studio workshop integrated into this workshop. The workshop-based education program was implemented for 6 hours per week, for a total of 72 hours in 3 months. At the end of the 3-month education, a post-test was applied to the students and the data were collected. SPSS 20.0 program was preferred to analyze the data. A dependent sample t-test was performed to understand whether there was a significant difference between the data. These tests are mostly used when analyzing repeated measurements (Büyüköztürk, 2011). During the workshop-based education, studies were carried out in the foreign language workshop established within the school and in the interactive studio workshop established integrated into this workshop. Students published a monthly English magazine called SEZENGLISH within the scope of the workshop studies. In addition, book translation studies were carried out from Turkish to English and from English to Turkish, and brochure studies were carried out including school promotion. In addition to these studies, podcasts were created in the interactive studio workshop and theater plays were performed in the target language. During the workshops, students were provided with a comfortable learning environment, they were given opportunities to conduct in-depth research, and their teachers guided them.

3. FINDINGS

In our study to measure the effect of workshop-based education on foreign language education, a dependent sample t-test was used to analyze the data. The analysis results are shared in Table 1.

Table 1

Dependent Sample T-Test Results Applied According to the “English Placement Test (Intermediate)” Data

Group	N	\bar{x}	s	sd	t	p
Ön_Test	30	60.50	2.69	23	12.713	0.03
Son_Test	30	79.38	2.86			

When the data analysis results were examined, it was seen that there was a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test data. It was understood that this difference was in favor of the post-test ($t(23) = 12.713$ $p < 0.05$). According to these results, the post-test data differed significantly from the pre-test data. It was understood from the research that the language education given to the students in the foreign language and interactive studio workshop for 3

months was beneficial. It is recommended to continue this education. In addition to the test data including the 4 basic skills, the students also had the opportunity to obtain their own products within the scope of the workshop studies. As mentioned before, these products were both printed and online studies such as magazines, books, brochures. In addition to these, the students also did practical activities. Thanks to these activities, students' awareness of foreign languages was increased. There are also studies similar to our study. Güngör (2014) applied a 12-week program in his study on students studying French language teaching in the foreign language education department. The education given within the scope of this program caused the students' listening comprehension skills to develop and their attitudes and behaviors towards the lesson to increase positively. It was also observed that students' vocabulary improved and their rate of correct pronunciation increased. Batdı and Şemerci (2012) determined that students' language and vocabulary skills improved in their studies by collecting data through surveys. According to the results of the study, there was an increase in language skills and especially pronunciation skills. Our research conducted within the school increased our students' language skills as well as contributing to their self-confidence and public speaking skills. The fact that our research was conducted in Kayseri province, that it was only for secondary education level and that it covered 9th and 10th grades are among the limitations of the study. When these limitations are considered, the study conducted was successful in its own content. There is a possibility of obtaining different results if different schools and different provinces are included in the study. Because not every school has similar opportunities and students at the same level. When such situations are considered, our study is at a level that can shed light on future studies.

4. CONCLUSION, DISCUSSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Before the workshop-based education, it was observed that the pre-test success average applied to the student group was $\bar{x}=60.50$. After the 3-month education, it was determined that the post-test success average was $\bar{x}=79.38$. Considering these results, it can be said that the workshop-based education contributed to the development of the students' language levels in 4 basic skills. When the analysis results and the feedback received from the students are examined, the workshop-based education given in the off-class times contributed to the development of the students' language levels, increase in their motivation levels and increase in the duration of their exposure to the language. In addition, it was observed that as a result of the education, the students did not see language learning only as a lesson and their awareness on this issue increased. It was determined that they enjoyed language learning more and had a good time since they obtained products such as magazines, books and brochures as a result of the education. The students showed great interest in the practical studies carried out in the interactive studio workshop opened as an integration with the foreign language workshop during the education. Thanks to the studies such as creating podcasts, theater plays and creating monthly bulletins carried out here, the students both developed their language skills and increased their computer skills thanks to technological opportunities. Within the scope of this study, workshop-based language education has been the subject of many national and international projects. Our students' studies have been disseminated thanks to projects such as TUBITAK, e-Twinning and Erasmus. Interest in our foreign language and interactive studio workshop has increased from state and private schools in the Kayseri region and our students' studies have been cited as examples. Our study was conducted in Kayseri province, and different studies covering the whole of Turkey can be conducted. At the same time, we conducted our study on high school students, and future studies can be conducted at primary and secondary school levels. Considering that not all schools in Turkey will have the same opportunities, studies can be conducted on a single workshop instead of a foreign language workshop and an interactive studio workshop. When such studies are supported, the interest,

desire and motivation levels of individuals learning the language increase, so these studies can be included in the curriculum. As it is known, high school level practical exams are conducted on speaking and listening. If the content of the speaking and listening exam is brought to a level where students can display their own performance, both the prejudice against the language will be broken and our students will be prevented from seeing the language as an exam. Practical exams can be more effective in the field as well as in theory thanks to such studies. Since we use the time outside of the class in our study, our students may not always be available. For this reason, if such studies are included in the course content, they can be more effective and efficient for both the student, the school and the teacher. As seen in our study, more efficient studies are carried out in workshops where students can feel special. If the number of foreign language workshops is increased throughout Turkey, all our students in our country can benefit from this service. Because thanks to such studies, students' sense of belonging increases and they feel special because they leave the school environment and their own classes.

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